

Orange3-ToxFairy
Widget usage examples
(visual guide)

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Orange basic add-ons

ToxFairy Add-on and widgets set:

- Auto-fill template
- Multifiles
- Combine HTS Objects
- HTS data filter
- Convert HTS data to Nexus
- HTS Preprocess
- Read HTS data/metadata
- TOX5 pie view
- TOX5 Score

"Welcome to Orange" shows some important basic functions: create a new project or open an existing one. There are also links with helpful information on how to work with Orange.

Click on the widget (or drag and drop) to place it on the Orange workspace

When mouse is over a widget, Orange shows additional description for widget general functionality and a tip with the **input** and **output** widget channels

Double click on the workflow widget to setup widget parameters

When your cursor is over a widget, into workspace, Orange shows a tip with the **input** and **output** widget channels

When connecting a widget to another multiple channels widget, as in the example workflow, we will get the following window asking users for information which channels to connect

Widgets can be connected using drag and drop from the output of the widget to the input of other widget

Orange workflows

You can access already created example workflows for TOX5 Scores Add-on

Or Save As... your own workflow.

Load workflow from basic_example.ows

You can use caLIBRAte dataset available at:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13683162>

Select multiple directories, one by one, or select multiple files.

For example select directories and remove one or many you don't need.

The output is a table with full path of selected directories

Select a widget to show its description.
See [workflow examples](#), [YouTube tutorials](#), or [welcome screen](#).

1. Enter endpoints name separate with *comma + space*
2. Entered endpoints will appear in next box. Choose dir and assay type for each endpoint from drop-down menus
3. Choose dir for template
4. Optional Recalculate dose button
If selected:
 - ✓ enter well volume in μl ;
 - ✓ enter plate growth area in cm^2 ;
 - ✓ choose recalculation method
5. Process and view resulting tables

The screenshot shows the 'Read HTS data/metadata' widget in the Orange data mining software. The interface is divided into two main sections: configuration and data view.

Configuration Section:

- Read and annotate data from local directory:**
 - Enter endpoints:** A text box containing 'ctg, dapi'.
 - Set proper dir:**
 - CTG:** A dropdown menu showing 'D:/PhD/projects/ToxPi/orange-tox5/toxfair'.
 - viability:** A dropdown menu.
 - DAPI:** A dropdown menu showing 'D:/PhD/projects/ToxPi/orange-tox5/toxfair'.
 - imaging:** A dropdown menu.
 - Set proper annotation dir:**
 - Annotation file:** A dropdown menu showing 'D:/PhD/projects/ToxPi/orange-tox5/toxfair'.
 - Recalculate dose:**
 - Recalculate Dose
 - Enter well volume in μl :** A text box containing '50'.
 - Enter plate growth area in cm^2 :** A text box containing '0.079495092'.
 - Dose per Cell Area ($\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$)
 - Dose based on Surface Area (cm^2/cm^2)
 - Cell Delivered Dose (cell delivered cm^2/cm^2)
 - Process:** A button at the bottom of the configuration section.

Data view Section:

- Data view:** A dropdown menu showing 'CTG'.
- Raw_data:** A dropdown menu showing 'Raw_data'.
- table:** A table displaying the resulting data. The table has columns for 'cells', 'replicates', and time points. The data is organized into rows for each cell/replicate combination.

From drop-down menus select endpoint and view data.

	cells	replicates			
0	A549	S1	0H		
1	BEAS-2B	S1	0H	6924	6351
2	A549	S1	24H	12558	14743
3	BEAS-2B	S1	24H	12558	14743
4	A549	S1	6H	10568	10930
5	BEAS-2B	S1	6H	10568	10930
6	A549	S2	0H	6409	7754
7	BEAS-2B	S2	0H	6409	7754
8	A549	S2	24H	17003	17800
9	BEAS-2B	S2	24H	17003	17800
10	A549	S2	6H	9002	10062
11	BEAS-2B	S2	6H	9002	10062

Save as

Read HTS data/metadata

Read HTS data/metadata - Orange

Read and annotate data from local directory

Enter endpoints:
ctg, dapi

Set proper dir
CTG
D:/PhD/projects/ToxPi/orange-tox5/toxfair
viability

DAPI
D:/PhD/projects/ToxPi/orange-tox5/toxfair

imaging

Set proper annotation dir

Annotation file
D:/PhD/projects/ToxPi/orange-t

Recalculate dose
 Recalculate Dose

Enter well volume in µl:
50

Enter plate growth area in cm2:
0.079495092

Dose per Cell Area (µg/cm²)
 Dose based on Surface Area
 Cell Delivered Dose (cell delivered cm²/cm²)

Process
11 → 16

Data view
CTG
Raw_data
table

	cells	replicates	time	A1	B1
0	A549	S1	0H	6924	6351
1	BEAS-2B	S1	0H	6924	6351
2	A549	S1	24H	12558	14743
3	BEAS-2B	S1	24H	12558	14743
4				10568	10930
5				10568	10930
6				6409	7754
7				6409	7754
8				17003	17800

Meta data: Table with 16 instances, 4 variables
Features: 4 categorical (12.5% missing values)

	index	material	concentration	SBET
1	A1	NANOFIL 9	73.62424772831...	24.1
2	B1	NANOFIL 9	220.8727431849...	24.1
3	C1	NANOFIL 9	662.6182295548...	24.1
4	D1	NANOFIL 9	1987.854688664...	24.1
5	E1	NANOFIL 9	5963.564065993...	24.1
6	F1	NANOFIL 9	17890.69219798...	24.1
7	G1	NANOFIL 9	53672.07659394...	24.1
8	H1	NANOFIL 9	161016.2297818...	24.1
9	A2	water	0.0	?
10	B2	water	0.0	?
11	C2	water	0.0	?
12	D2	water	0.0	?
13	E2	water	0.0	?
14	F2	water	0.0	?

View recalculated doses in output

Extract as a table

Data Table - Orange

Info
16 instances
4 features (12.5% missing data)
No target variable.
No meta attributes.

Variables
 Show variable labels (if present)
 Visualize numeric values

Restore Original Order

Send Automatically

	index	material	concentration	SBET
1	A1	NANOFIL 9	73.62424772831...	24.1
2	B1	NANOFIL 9	220.8727431849...	24.1
3	C1	NANOFIL 9	662.6182295548...	24.1
4	D1	NANOFIL 9	1987.854688664...	24.1
5	E1	NANOFIL 9	5963.564065993...	24.1
6	F1	NANOFIL 9	17890.69219798...	24.1
7	G1	NANOFIL 9	53672.07659394...	24.1
8	H1	NANOFIL 9	161016.2297818...	24.1

Endpoints from *Read HTS data/metadata* can be selected and separately processed.

All preprocessed data is available for preview. Select endpoint, then select type of resulting data: normalized data, mean data, median data, dose-response data. Each shown table can be saved.

Select endpoint

Choose normalization methods

Normalize each endpoint separately

Combine technical replicates if have

Calculate dose-response parameters for all normalized endpoints

HTS preprocess - Orange

Tox5

- DAPIA
- DAPIB
- CASP
- H2AX
- 8OHG

Normalizations

- Remove failed images
- Remove outliers
- Percent of control
- Percent effect of control
- Mean and Median of replicates

Technical replicates

- Combine technical replicates

Dose - response

- Dose - response

Preprocess

Data view

CASP

Normalized

	cells	replicates	time	A1	A2
0	BEAS-2B	S1	24H	-20.0566973777...	-6.52019844082.
1	BEAS-2B	S1	6H	58.63448275862...	53.46206896551
2	BEAS-2B	S1	72H	-9.17431192660...	-105.587989991.
3	BEAS-2B	S2	24H	9.155555555555555	12.0711111111111
4	BEAS-2B	S2	6H	16.92307692307...	20.20066889632
5	BEAS-2B	S2	72H	-83.1692913385...	-14.0748031496.
6	BEAS-2B	S3	24H	38.23781009409...	19.76047904191
7	BEAS-2B	S3	6H	74.85401459854...	73.60097323600
8	BEAS-2B	S3	72H	22.05578512396...	-0.30991735537.
9	BEAS-2B	S4	24H	41.94078947368...	33.60745614035

Save as

Slice automatically pattern

Select one or multiple cell lines →

Select transforming function from drop-down menu →

Select slicing pattern: First two patterns are **automatically generated**, and created slices will be shown in the right box "Slices" →

Calculate tox5 scores →

Tox5 Score - Orange

Tox5-scores

Select cell lines:

- BEAS-2B
- A549

Select transforming functions:

1st significant dose

log10x_6

Area under curve

- sqrt_x
- log10x_6
- sqrt_x
- yeo_johnson

Select slicing pattern

Slice by time-endpoint

Slice by endpoint

Slice manually

Calculate tox5 scores

Slices

Set weight:

Add weight

Clear weight

Remove selected slices

	BEAS-2B_24H_CTG	BEAS-2B_24H_DAPI
0	BEAS-2B_24H_AUC_CTG	BEAS-2B_24H_AUC_DAPI
1	BEAS-2B_24H_1st_2SD_CTG	BEAS-2B_24H_1st_2SD_DAPI
2	BEAS-2B_24H_1st_3SD_CTG	BEAS-2B_24H_1st_3SD_DAPI
3	BEAS-2B_24H_MAX_CTG	BEAS-2B_24H_MAX_DAPI

Automatically created slices by pattern:
"Slice by time-endpoint"

Slice manually pattern

TOX5 Score

The screenshot shows the 'Tox5 Score - Orange' software interface. On the left, the 'Tox5-scores' panel is configured with cell lines 'BEAS-2B' and 'A549', and transforming functions 'log10x_6', 'sqrt_x', and 'log10x_6'. The 'Slices' panel shows two custom slices: 'Custom slice 1' and 'Custom slice 2'. 'Custom slice 2' is highlighted with an orange rounded rectangle and contains parameters for BEAS-2B_24H_MAX_CTG, BEAS-2B_6H_MAX_CTG, BEAS-2B_24H_AUC_DAPI, BEAS-2B_6H_AUC_DAPI, BEAS-2B_24H_1st_2SD_DAPI, BEAS-2B_6H_1st_2SD_DAPI, BEAS-2B_24H_1st_3SD_DAPI, and BEAS-2B_6H_1st_3SD_DAPI. The 'Manual slicing' panel on the right has a 'Load parameters' button at the top, a list of parameters in the middle, and a 'Create slice' button at the bottom. The 'Slice name' field is set to 'Custom slice 2'. Orange arrows point from text labels to these specific UI elements.

Manual slicing

Load parameters

BEAS-2B_24H_AUC_CTG
BEAS-2B_6H_AUC_CTG
BEAS-2B_24H_1st_2SD_CTG
BEAS-2B_6H_1st_2SD_CTG
BEAS-2B_24H_1st_3SD_CTG
BEAS-2B_6H_1st_3SD_CTG
BEAS-2B_24H_MAX_CTG
BEAS-2B_6H_MAX_CTG
BEAS-2B_24H_AUC_DAPI
BEAS-2B_6H_AUC_DAPI
BEAS-2B_24H_1st_2SD_DAPI
BEAS-2B_6H_1st_2SD_DAPI
BEAS-2B_24H_1st_3SD_DAPI
BEAS-2B_6H_1st_3SD_DAPI
BEAS-2B_24H_MAX_DAPI
BEAS-2B_6H_MAX_DAPI

Slice name:
Custom slice 2

Create slice

Load available dose-response parameters

Select parameters to be included in the slice

Set a slice name

Create a slice

Add weight to selected metrics and remove chosen slices

Tox5 Score - Orange

Tox5-scores

Select cell lines:

BEAS-2B
A549

Select transforming functions:

1st significant dose
log10x_6

Area under curve
sqrt_x

Maximum dose
log10x_6

Select slicing pattern

Slice by time-endpoint
 Slice by endpoint
 Slice manually

Calculate tox5 scores

Slices

Set weight:

1. 5
3. Add weight

Clear weight

Remove selected slices

	BEAS-2B_6H_CTG	BEAS-2B_6H_DAPI	BEAS-2B_24H_CTG
0	BEAS-2B_6H_AUC_CTG	BEAS-2B_6H_AUC_DAPI	BEAS-2B_24H_AUC_CTG
1	BEAS-2B_6H_1st_2SD_CTG	BEAS-2B_6H_1st_2SD_DAPI	BEAS-2B_24H_1st_2SD_CTG
2	BEAS-2B_6H_1st_3SD_CTG_(3)	BEAS-2B_6H_1st_3SD_DAPI_(3)	BEAS-2B_24H_1st_3SD_CTG
2. 3	BEAS-2B_6H_MAX_CTG_(5)	BEAS-2B_6H_MAX_DAPI	BEAS-2B_24H_MAX_CTG

Remove selected slices button will delete all selected columns (slices).

1. Enter weight to *Set weight* field,
2. Select multiple or one metrics and
3. *Add weight*

Added weight will be represented in () as a suffix after metric name. Also added weights can be removed from *Clear weight* button.

Select materials for plot

- Tox5 pie view
- 4-Nitroquinoline 1-oxide
- Daunorubicin
- Gemcitabine
- Mitomycin C
- Tylose HS 6000 YP2
- tetrapotassium diphosphat
- A1 Silver nanoparticles
- Tylose HX 6000 YG4
- Talcum
- 5-Fluorouracil
- Dolomite
- A2 Silver nanoparticles (less
- Non-Porous Silica 300nm-C
- Titanium(IV)oxide
- CuO nanoparticles
- Non-porous Silica 100nm-M
- Expancel
- Porous Silica 300nm-CuO c
- PoleStar 200P
- Porous Silica 100nm-Me
- TiO2/SiO2 1:3
- Sodiumhexametaphosphat
- Porous Silica 300nm-Me
- TiO2
- Non-porous Silica 300nm-M
- Calcium Carbonate
- Porous Silica 100nm-CuO c
- Ultrax 96
- Alumino Silica
- water

Select colored pattern for slices

- Select colored parameter
- endpoint
- Change ci low color
- Change ci high color
- Plot Image
- Save Image

BEAS-2B_72H_80HG	BEAS-2B_72H_DAPI
BEAS-2B_6H_80HG	BEAS-2B_6H_DAPI
BEAS-2B_24H_80HG	BEAS-2B_24H_DAPI
BEAS-2B_72H_CASP	BEAS-2B_72H_H2AX
BEAS-2B_6H_CASP	BEAS-2B_6H_H2AX
BEAS-2B_24H_CASP	BEAS-2B_24H_H2AX

Change color for low and high bounds of confidence interval, if they are calculated

Toxpi Ranked materials

Mitomycin C 0.49

A1 Silver nanoparticles 0.28

HTS data filter

	cells	replicates	time	
0	A549	S1	0H	176
1	BEAS-2B	S1	0H	540
2	HEPG2	S1	0H	809
3	THP-1	S1	0H	152

Filtrate the data based on selected: endpoints, cell lines and materials.

Load workflow with test data from basic_example_test_data.ows

Select test data

Use "Select test data" to access data prepared for testing.
Two directories: raw_data (CTG data) and raw_data_imaging (DAPI, OHG, H2AX data).
Two Templates one empty and one ready.

Select test data

Select files

Select directories

raw_data
raw_data_imaging

clear output

Read HTS data/metadata - Orange

Read and annotate data from local directory

Enter endpoints:
ctg, dapi

Set proper dir
CTG

DAPI
d:\phd\projects\toxpi\orange-tox5\tox5_pr

Set proper annotation dir

Annotation file
d:\phd\projects\toxpi\orange-tox5\tox5_pr

Recalculate dose

Recalculate Dose

Enter well volume in µl:
50

Enter plate growth area in cm2:
0.079495092

Dose per Cell Area (µg/cm²)

Dose based on Surface Area (cm²/cm²)

Cell Delivered Dose (cell delivered cm²/cm²)

Process

Data view

CTG

	cells	replicates	time	A1	B1	
0	A549	S1	0H	19032	21056	22
1	BEAS-2B	S1	0H	6924	6351	71
2	A549	S1	24H	29360	29428	33
3	BEAS-2B	S1	24H	12558	14743	12
4	A549	S1	6H	18060	23088	22
5	BEAS-2B	S1	6H	10568	10930	10
6	A549	S2	0H	21389	21037	23
7	BEAS-2B	S2	0H	6409	7754	77
8	A549	S2	24H	53075	51216	52
9	BEAS-2B	S2	24H	17003	17800	16
10	A549	S2	6H	28295	29055	28
11	BEAS-2B	S2	6H	9002	10062	10
material	None	None	None	NANOFIL 9	NANOFIL 9	NA
concentration	nan	nan	nan	73.62424772831...	220.8727431849...	66

Save as

Select test data (1) - Orange

Select test data

Select files

Select directories

TestDataRecordingForm_harmless HTS_METADATA_empty.xlsx
TestDataRecordingForm_harmless HTS_METADATA_ready.xlsx

clear output

HTS METADATA TEMPLATE

Empty template

1	Replicate	Time	Endpoint	Cell	Date	filename
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If the file name does not correspond with the template structure in sheet "Files" (replicate_time_endpoint_cell_date) manually correct errors.

1	Replicate	Time	Endpoint	Cell	Date	filename
2	S1	0h	CTG	A549	test	S1_0h_CTG_A549_test.csv
3	S1	0h	CTG	BEAS-2B	test	S1_0h_CTG_BEAS-2B_test.csv
4	S1	24h	CTG	A549	test	S1_24h_CTG_A549_test.csv
5	S1	24h	CTG	BEAS-2B	test	S1_24h_CTG_BEAS-2B_test.csv
6	S1	6h	CTG	A549	test	S1_6h_CTG_A549_test.csv
7	S1	6h	CTG	BEAS-2B	test	S1_6h_CTG_BEAS-2B_test.csv
8	S2	0h	CTG	A549	test	S2_0h_CTG_A549_test.csv
9	S2	0h	CTG	BEAS-2B	test	S2_0h_CTG_BEAS-2B_test.csv
10	S2	24h	CTG	A549	test	S2_24h_CTG_A549_test.csv
11	S2	24h	CTG	BEAS-2B	test	S2_24h_CTG_BEAS-2B_test.csv
12	S2	6h	CTG	A549	test	S2_6h_CTG_A549_test.csv
13	S2	6h	CTG	BEAS-2B	test	S2_6h_CTG_BEAS-2B_test.csv
14	S1	24h	A549			S1_24h_A549.txt
15	S1	24h	BEAS-2B			S1_24h_BEAS-2B.txt
16	S1	6h	A549			S1_6h_A549.txt
17	S1	6h	BEAS-2B			S1_6h_BEAS-2B.txt
18	S2	24h	A549			S2_24h_A549.txt
19	S2	24h	BEAS-2B			S2_24h_BEAS-2B.txt
20	S2	6h	A549			S2_6h_A549.txt
21	S2	6h	BEAS-2B			S2_6h_BEAS-2B.txt

Files sheet after using "Auto-fill HTS Template" widget

1	Replicate	Time	Endpoint	Cell	Date	filename
2	S1	0h	CTG	A549	test	S1_0h_CTG_A549_test.csv
3	S1	0h	CTG	BEAS-2B	test	S1_0h_CTG_BEAS-2B_test.csv
4	S1	24h	CTG	A549	test	S1_24h_CTG_A549_test.csv
5	S1	24h	CTG	BEAS-2B	test	S1_24h_CTG_BEAS-2B_test.csv
6	S1	6h	CTG	A549	test	S1_6h_CTG_A549_test.csv
7	S1	6h	CTG	BEAS-2B	test	S1_6h_CTG_BEAS-2B_test.csv
8	S2	0h	CTG	A549	test	S2_0h_CTG_A549_test.csv
9	S2	0h	CTG	BEAS-2B	test	S2_0h_CTG_BEAS-2B_test.csv
10	S2	24h	CTG	A549	test	S2_24h_CTG_A549_test.csv
11	S2	24h	CTG	BEAS-2B	test	S2_24h_CTG_BEAS-2B_test.csv
12	S2	6h	CTG	A549	test	S2_6h_CTG_A549_test.csv
13	S2	6h	CTG	BEAS-2B	test	S2_6h_CTG_BEAS-2B_test.csv
14	S1	24h	dapi, h2ax, 8ohg	A549		S1_24h_A549.txt
15	S1	24h	dapi, h2ax, 8ohg	BEAS-2B		S1_24h_BEAS-2B.txt
16	S1	6h	dapi, h2ax, 8ohg	A549		S1_6h_A549.txt
17	S1	6h	dapi, h2ax, 8ohg	BEAS-2B		S1_6h_BEAS-2B.txt
18	S2	24h	dapi, h2ax, 8ohg	A549		S2_24h_A549.txt
19	S2	24h	dapi, h2ax, 8ohg	BEAS-2B		S2_24h_BEAS-2B.txt
20	S2	6h	dapi, h2ax, 8ohg	A549		S2_6h_A549.txt
21	S2	6h	dapi, h2ax, 8ohg	BEAS-2B		S2_6h_BEAS-2B.txt

Example after manually corrected "Endpoint" and "Cell" columns

Do not correct actual file names and "filename" column

1	Partner	HMGU		Study name
2	Operator			
4	Annotation			
5	Well Address	Sample name	Sample code	Concentration (yg/ml)
6	A1	NANOFIL 9	20	0.11705532693187
7	B1	NANOFIL 9	20	0.351165981
8	C1	NANOFIL 9	20	1.053497942
9	D1	NANOFIL 9	20	3.160493827
10	E1	NANOFIL 9	20	9.481481481

Select "Front sheet" and manually fill metadata for each column. "Sample name" column must be filled using the drop down menu.

Template Wizard : metadata templates

H2020 HARMLESS - eNanoMapper database

Type

Metadata including links to data files

Excel template download

Download template

Project

Partner/organisation

Work Package

HARMLESS

MISVIK - Misvik Biology OY

WP3: New Approach Methodc

Materials table - all materials will be available for selection in the Excel file

Show 10 entries

1. Download HTS_METADATA template

Before Auto-fill template

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	Replicate	Time	Endpoint	Cell	Date	filename
2						
3						
4						
5						
6						
7						

2. Select your data directories

4. Auto-fill template

All metadata from each file name will be added automatically into cells: Replicate, Time, Endpoint, Cell, filename. Any additional metadata and inconsistency need to be correct manually.

3. Select your template path

5. When you are ready with manually corrections and additions, reconnect template path (with already completed template) with Read HTS data/metadata widget.

After Auto-fill template

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	Replicate	Time	Endpoint	Cell	Date	filename
2	S1	0h	Casp	A549	06062022	S1_0h_Casp_A549_06062022.csv
3	S1	0h	Casp	BEAS-2B	02052022	S1_0h_Casp_BEAS-2B_02052022.csv
4	S1	0h	Casp	HepG2	06062022	S1_0h_Casp_HepG2_06062022.csv
5	S1	0h	Casp	THP-1	02052022	S1_0h_Casp_THP-1_02052022.csv
6	S1	0h	CTG	A549	06062022	S1_0h_CTG_A549_06062022.csv
7	S1	0h	CTG	BEAS-2B	02052022	S1_0h_CTG_BEAS-2B_02052022.csv
8	S1	0h	CTG	HepG2	06062022	S1_0h_CTG_HepG2_06062022.csv
9	S1	0h	CTG	THP-1	02052022	S1_0h_CTG_THP-1_02052022.csv

Try basic_example_with_autofill_tmp.ows ready workflow to autofill template.

Select empty template.

Select directories from test data

When you are ready with corrections and updates to new filled template, read the data.

Replicate	Time	Endpoint	Cell	Date	filename

Select empty Template

Auto-fill HTS template will fill the template "files" sheet with data from selected test data directories. Open the fill template and compare with existing ready template. Complete the information in sheet "Front sheet" and "files".

Load workflow from calibrate_set1_w_wo.ows

Use caLIBRAte dataset set1 or set2 available at:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13683162>

Combine with/without serum

FAIRificate and save data as Nexus, which could visualize at:
<https://h5web.ideaconsult.net/>

Materials from one dataset

HTS preprocess - Orange

Tox5

- CTG
- DAPI
- H2AX
- 8OHG
- CASP

Normalizations

- Remove outliers
- Percent of control
- Percent effect of control
- Baseline correction
- Baseline correction as percent
- Normalize Caspase to cell amount
- Mean and Median of replicates

Technical replicates

- Combine technical replicates

Dose - response

- Dose - response

Data view

CTG

Dose-response

table	549_24H_AUC_CT	549_6H_AUC_CT
ZnCdSeS	0.0	114.574
0.05% BSA water, 30ul EtOH	nan	nan
ZnCuInS/ZnS	0.0	56.0562

Save as

Combined materials

Combine HTS Objects - Orange

Combine HTS Objects

- Combine by different materials
- Combine +/- serum used

Data view

CTG

Dose-response

table	549_24H_AUC_CT	549_6H_AUC_CT	549_72H_AUC_CT
ZnCdSeS	0.0	114.5747800825...	0.0
0.05% BSA water, 30ul EtOH	nan	nan	nan
ZnCuInS/ZnS	0.0	56.05626061029...	0.0
NM-105	0.0	87.86843032244...	0.0
JRCNM01005a	0.0	68.6099765091525	0.0
NM-220	34.01668174969...	86.61876785478...	0.0
JRCNM50001a	51.15229661585...	67.53705374304...	0.0
NM-110	0.0	226.5677505246...	34.823179

Save as

Materials from another dataset

HTS preprocess (1) - Orange

Tox5

- CTG
- DAPI
- H2AX
- 8OHG
- CASP

Normalizations

- Remove outliers
- Percent of control
- Percent effect of control
- Baseline correction
- Baseline correction as percent
- Normalize Caspase to cell amount
- Mean and Median of replicates

Technical replicates

- Combine technical replicates

Dose - response

- Dose - response

Data view

CTG

Dose-response

table	549_24H_AUC_CT	549_6H_AUC_CT
NM-105	0.0	87.8684303224
JRCNM01005a	0.0	68.6099765091
water	nan	nan
NM-220	34.01668174969...	86.6187678547
JRCNM50001a	51.15229661585...	67.5370537430
NM-110	0.0	226.567750524

Preprocess

Save as

Convert HTS processed data to Nexus file format

Convert HTS processed data to Nexus file format

Read and explore Nexus file in: <https://h5web.ideaconsult.net/>

Choose dir where .nxs file will be saved

Convert HTS processed data to Nexus file format - Orange

Convert HTS processed data to Nexus file format

Enter substance owner:

HARMLESS

Enter data provider:

Misvik

Choose Save Directory

Selected Directory: D:\PhD

Enter filename:

Quantum_Dots_substances

Convert to Nexus file

Resulting message: Nexus file is saved in D:\PhD\Quantum_Dots_substances.nxs

Enter a file name

Convert to Nexus

TOX5 score workflow can be extended with basic Orange widgets.

- View output table with Data Table widget,
- Save it with Save Data widget

Feature Statistics - Orange

Name	Distribution	Mean	Mode	Median	Dispersion	Min.	Max.	Missing
toxpi_score		0.277852	0.179145	0.258707	0.329717	0.179145	0.739752	0 (0 %)
rnk		23.5	1	23.5	0.564933	1	46	0 (0 %)
THP-1_72H_MAX_CASP		0.691258	0.00	0.721844	0.304168	0.00	1	0 (0 %)
THP-1_6H_MAX_CASP		0.729695	0.00	0.813788	0.321801	0.00	1	0 (0 %)
THP-1_24H_MAX_CASP		0.784148	0.00	0.836326	0.275576	0.00	1	0 (0 %)
HEPG2_72H_MAX_CASP		0.873464	0.00	0.921762	0.203529	0.00	1	0 (0 %)

Color: rnk

Send Automatically

Data Table - Orange

Info
46 instances (no missing data)
16 features
No target variable.
No meta attributes.

Variables
 Show variable labels (if present)
 Visualize numeric values
 Color by instance classes

Selection
 Select full rows

Restore Original Order

Send Automatically

index	Material	toxpi_score	rnk	HEPG2_24H_CASP	HEPG2_24H_CTG
1	3	4NQO	0.978289	1	1
2	38	MMC	0.566975	2	0.386942
3	9	Bleom	0.460991	3	0.970482
4	30	NANOFIL 9	0.402897	4	0.283508
5	14	CuO	0.356274	5	0.303916
6	4	XE2B	0.331173	6	0.418548
7	19	NRCWE-058	0.305542	7	0.378606
8	22	BENTONITE	0.288309	8	0.24686
9	12	CO3O4	0.268857	9	0.0129127
10	20	NRCWE-056	0.202002	10	0.163222
11	17	NRCWE-042	0.192465	11	0.271534
12	43	NANOFIL 3000 SE	0.189705	12	0.439737
13	5	JRCNM04001a	0.185627	13	0.107508
14	32	JRCNM04003a	0.18536	14	0.425441
15	37	FE2COO4 1/1	0.181561	15	0.048333
16	27	Flamrus101	0.180062	16	0.320045

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- View dose-response parameters statistics after applied transforming functions

Save Data - Orange

Add type annotations to header

Autosave when receiving new data

Save Save as ...

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Basic Orange widgets

